

JCMST

NOVI SAD

2023

Supported by the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Science, Technological development and Innovation of the republic of Serbia

ABSTRACT BOOK

11 – 13 October 2023

Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad

Novi Sad, Serbia

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

61(048.3)

THE PSU-UNS Joint Conference on Medical Science and Technology (2 ; 2023 ; Novi Sad)

Abstract book [Elektronski izvor] / The 2nd PSU-UNS Joint Conference on Medical Science and Technology 2023, 11-13 October 2023, Novi Sad, Serbia ; [editor-in-chief Rajko Jović]. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Medicine, 2023. - 1 USB fleš memorija

Tiraž 150.

ISBN 978-86-7197-742-5

а) Медицинске науке -- Нове технологије -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 126492937

Advisory Committee

Dejan Madić, Full Prof., Rector of the University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Asst. Prof. Dr. Niwat Keawpradub, President, Prince of Songkla University, Thailand

Snežana Brkić, Full Prof., Dean of the Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, Serbia

Assoc. Prof. Roengsak Leetanaporn, MD Dean of the Faculty of Medicine, PSU,
Thailand

Zoran Gojković, Assoc. Prof., Provincial Secretary for Healthcare

Zoran Milošević, Full Prof., Provincial Secretary for Higher Education and Scientific
Research

Scientific Committee

President Duško Kozić, Prof. Dr., Vice Dean for Research, MFNS, Serbia

Co-President Assoc. Prof. Teerha Piratvisuth, MD Vice Dean for
International Affairs

Scientific Committee Members

Snežana Brkić, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Branislav Bajkin, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Zoran Komazec, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Biljana Srdić-Galić, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Biljana Vučković, Assoc. Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Dragan Kravarušić, Full Prof., University of Tel Aviv "Sackler" Faculty of Medicine, Israel

Ludovico Abenavoli, Full Prof., University Magna Graecia of Catanzaro, Italy

Prof. Tippawan Liabsuetrakul, M.D., Ph.D. / Vice Dean for Research, Faculty of
Medicine, PSU

Joint Conference on
Medical Science and
Technology
NOVI SAD
2023

Prof. Surasak Sangkhathat, M.D., Ph.D. / Assistant Dean for Research, Faculty of Medicine, PSU

Pasuree Sangsupawanich, M.D., Ph.D. / Assistant Dean for Hospital Affairs, Faculty of Medicine, PSU

Prof. Boonsin Tangtrakulwanich, M.D. / Head of the Department of Orthopedics, Faculty of Medicine, PSU

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Srisurang Suttapreyasri / Associate Dean for Research and Graduate Studies, Faculty of Dentistry, PSU

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Karnsunaphat Balthip / Associate Dean for Research, Social Alliance, and International Affairs, Faculty of Nursing, PSU

Local Organizational Committee

Goran Stojiljković, Full Prof.

Mirela Erić, Full Prof.

Otto Barak, Full Prof.

Milica Jeremić-Knežević, Assoc. Prof.

Jasmina Boban, Assist. Prof.

Vedrana Karan Rakić, Assist. Prof.

Dubravka Klajić

Position 47

DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE ENGAGEMENT OF CHILDREN WITH DEVELOPMENTAL DISABILITIES AND TYPICALLY DEVELOPING CHILDREN IN EVERYDAY ACTIVITIES

Sanela Slavković¹, Špela Golubović², Tatjana Krstić³, Nina Brkić-Jovanović⁴, Vesela Milankov⁵

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Department of special education and rehabilitation, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

sanela.slavkovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Department of special education and rehabilitation, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

spela.golubovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Department of psychology, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

tatjana.krstic@mf.uns.ac.rs

⁴University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Department of psychology, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

nina.brkic-jovanovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

⁵University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Department of special education and rehabilitation, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

vesela.milankov@mf.uns.ac.rs

Introduction: Engagement represents a child's involvement in various life situations. Creating opportunities for children to develop their skills and abilities, enable them to fully engage in activities and occupations that are typically expected for their age. Two guiding research questions for the present study were to:

- a) describe the correlation between the levels of engagement in different types of activities relative to children with developmental disabilities (CwDD) and typically-developing children and their enjoyment in them;
- b) determine whether engagement is associated with the level of functional status in both groups of children.

Materials and methods: The sample comprised 199 preschool children between ages 3 and 6 (typically-developing children n=125; CwDD n=74). Both groups were equal in terms of age, as well as their parents' age, education level and employment status. The following instruments were used: General questionnaire; Child Engagement in Daily Life measure (Chiarello et al., 2013), a parent-completed measure comprising questions regarding child's engagement in family and recreational activities (11 items), and part II covering self-care domain (7 items); Functional Status II (Stein & Jessop, 1991), a 14-item measure used for evaluating a child's functioning.

Joint Conference on
Medical Science and
Technology
NOVI SAD
2023

Results: There was no difference between children with and without disabilities in terms of the level of their activity engagement. However, parents of CwDD estimated their children were less likely to enjoy activities involving manipulative skills and sports. Higher functional status is related to higher activity engagement and perceptions of enjoyment of activities, and in turn to higher activity levels within self-care domain in both study groups ($p < 0.01$).

Conclusions: Engaging CwDD in various activities and environments may help them develop their abilities and skills. We can conclude that children's involvement in preschool programs is the necessary precondition for their full engagement.

Keywords: engagement, children, functional status, children with disabilities, early intervention